

D2D CRC Law and Policy Deliverable D.C3.1

Project C

***DC25008: Compliance by Design (CbD)
and Compliance through Design (CtD).***

***Solutions to support automated
information sharing.***

December 20, 2018
(Revision: March 28th and June 24th 2019)

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.3271464](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3271464)

Law and Policy Program
Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre
La Trobe University

2D CRC Law and Policy Project team members

Report Authors:

Research Professor Pompeu Casanovas, Project Led, La Trobe Law School, and Professor Louis de Koker, Program Lead.

Legal Team:

Professor Louis de Koker, Program Lead, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University
 Research Professor Pompeu Casanovas, Project C Lead, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Professor Patrick Keyzer, Key Researcher, Head of La Trobe Law School, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Professor Danuta Mendelson, Key Researcher, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, Deakin Law School

Professor David Watts, Key Researcher, Key Researcher, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Dr. Jeff Barnes, Key Researcher, Senior Lecturer, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Dr. Suzanne O'Toole, Key Researcher, Lecturer, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Mira Stammers, Key Researcher, Lecturer, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Hon. David Parsons, Adjunct Professor, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University

Scientific Team:

Dr. Guido Governatori, Sub-Project Lead, Software Systems Research Group, Data61 Legal Informatics Team Leader, Law and Policy Program, D2D CRC, La Trobe University, CSIRO, Brisbane

Dr. Víctor Rodríguez-Doncel, Sub-Project Lead, D2D CRC Program, La Trobe University, Ontology Engineering Group (OEG), Artificial Intelligence Department, Polytechnic University of Madrid

Dr. Mustafa Hashmi, Key Researcher, D2D CRC Program, La Trobe University, Data61

Dr. Jorge Rodríguez-Doncel, Key Researcher, Executive Head AB Institute for Law and Technology, D2D CRC Program, La Trobe University, Autonomous University of Barcelona

Version	Author	Tasks	Date
DC3.1 vs1	Louis de Koker	Spent Convictions Scheme Workflow	September 28 th 2018
DC3.1 vs2	Pompeu Casanovas	Narrative, Development, References	October 10 th 2018
DC3.1 vs3	Mira Stammers	Review	October 16 th 2018
DC3.1 vs4	Louis de Koker and Pompeu Casanovas	Updating and revision	December 5 th 2018
DC3.1 vs5	Pompeu Casanovas and Louis de Koker	Updating, revision, and alignment with DC3-2-8	March 28 th 2019
DC3.1 vs6	Daniel Mckintosh	Proofreading	April 24 th 2019
DC3.1 vs7	Pompeu Casanovas and Louis de Koker	Final version	June 24 th 2019

Law and Policy Deliverable D.C3.1

Spent Convictions Use Case. Preliminary Notes.

By Pompeu Casanovas and Louis de Koker

Independent research report commissioned by the Australian Criminal
Intelligence Commission (NCIS Pilot Program)

AUSTRALIAN
**CRIMINAL
INTELLIGENCE
COMMISSION**

Table of Contents

Acronyms	5
Executive Summary	6
1 Introduction	7
2 Use Case	7
2.1 Spent Convictions	7
2.2 Questions.....	7
3 Elaborating on the analysis	18
3.1 Who, what, when, where, why, in what way, by what means?	18
3.2 Definition.....	19
4 Crimes Act 1914 (Part VIIC)	19
5 When is a conviction spent?	20
6 Limited right of non-disclosure: when does an individual have a right not to disclose their conviction?	20
7 Exclusions (Exception to the right)	21
8 Breaches (lodging a complaint)	21
9 Privacy Act 1988	22
10 Commonwealth Spent Convictions Scheme Guide	23
11 Criticisms	24
11.1 What is the legal value of a ‘scheme’	24
11.2 Spent Convictions	25
11.3 Critical scholarship	26
12 Australia Human Rights Commission on Spent Convictions (2008)	27
13 Wales and England (Rehabilitation of Offenders Act 1974)	28
14 References	30

Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
CbD	Compliance by Design
CtD	Compliance through Design
D2 CRC	Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre
NLP	Natural Language Processing
SCS	Spent Convictions Scheme

Executive Summary

This Deliverable includes the preliminary conceptual work and notes on Spent Convictions prior to its semi-automated modelling. DC3.1 introduces the subject. DC3.2 presents the clustering for the survey on legal compliance. DC3.3 presents the roadmap towards publishing law as data using Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools. DC3.4 describes in more detail the Spent Convictions Scheme (SCE). DC3.5 elaborates on the potential interpretative issues and impact of Crimes Act 1914 (Cth) – Part VIIC – Division 3: Sections 85ZV, 85ZW and Associated Definitions. DC3.6 analyses the case law perspective. DC3.7 carries out the semantic modelling of Spent Convictions in defeasible semantic logic. DC3.8 summarises and evaluates the legal findings of the Project.

The present Deliverable: (i) introduces the use case on Spent Convictions; (ii) formulates the questions to be answered following the Spent Convictions Scheme; (iii) defines a preliminary legal framework; (iv) summarises some criticisms to the SCS formulated from the legal and criminological point of view by the doctrine.

1 Introduction

The work presented in this document has been made in the context of Project C, “Compliance by Design (CbD) and Compliance through Design (CtD) solutions to support automated information sharing”, within the Law and Policy Program, Data to Decisions Cooperative Research Centre (D2D CRC).

The following use case is to assist the development of automated access decision support for the proposed future National Criminal Intelligence System (NCIS). These will be workshopped, worked out, and refined to best serve the objectives of this project and possible end-user needs.

2 Use Case

2.1 Spent Convictions

Example 1: Person A

Purpose	Vetting for an appointment as a management consultant to the Australian Federal Police
Coordinating jurisdiction (CJ)	Federal
Originating jurisdiction of Police History Information (PHI)	Federal
PHI	Insider trading (s 1043A(1) of the Corporations Act 2001 (Cth) (2 charges); convicted on 10 August 1998 Released on entering a good behaviour bond for 2 years.

Relevant legislation: [Part VIIC of the Crimes Act 1914](#) (Part VIIC)

Helpful overview: <https://www.oaic.gov.au/individuals/privacy-fact-sheets/general/privacy-fact-sheet-41-commonwealth-spent-convictions-scheme>

2.2 Questions

Question	Legal rule
	Is the conviction spent?
Does this enquiry concern a natural person or a body corporate?	S 85ZP(2) A reference in this Part to a person convicted of an offence does not include a reference to a body corporate.

<p>Should the person be taken to have been convicted of an offence, for purposes of the spent conviction scheme?</p> <p>Has the person been convicted of an offence (whether summarily or on indictment, of the offence) that has not been quashed or set aside?</p> <p>or</p> <p>Has the person has been charged with, and found guilty of, the offence but discharged without conviction and the finding has not been quashed or set aside?</p> <p>or</p> <p>Has the person not been found guilty of the offence, but a court has taken it into account in passing sentence on the person for another offence of which the person was convicted and that conviction not been quashed or set aside?</p>	<p>S 85ZL: spent, in relation to a conviction, has the meaning given it in section 85ZM.</p> <p>S 85ZM: For the purposes of this Part, a person shall be taken to have been convicted of an offence if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the person has been convicted, whether summarily or on indictment, of the offence; (b) the person has been charged with, and found guilty of, the offence but discharged without conviction; or (c) the person has not been found guilty of the offence, but a court has taken it into account in passing sentence on the person for another offence. <p>For the purposes of this Part, a person’s conviction of an offence is spent if:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) the person has been granted a pardon for a reason other than that the person was wrongly convicted of the offence; or (b) the person was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence, or was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence for more than 30 months, and the waiting period for the offence has ended. <p>Comment: Convictions would be recorded but not guilt findings not resulting in a conviction or reflected in a sentence of another offence?</p> <p>S 85ZN: quashing)</p> <p>For the purposes of this Part, a person’s conviction of an offence shall be taken to have been quashed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a) where the person was convicted of the offence—if the conviction has been quashed or set aside; (b) where the person was found guilty of the offence, but discharged without conviction—if the finding of guilt has been quashed or set aside; or (c) where the person was not found guilty of the offence, but a court has taken it into account in passing sentence on the person for another offence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) if the person’s conviction of the other offence has been quashed or set aside; or (ii) if the court’s decision to take the offence into account has been set aside.
<p>If so,</p>	<p>85ZR Pardons for persons wrongly convicted</p>

<p>Has the person has been granted a pardon (whether for a wrongful conviction under s 85ZR or for a reason other than that the person was wrongly convicted of the offence?</p>	<p>(1) Despite any other Commonwealth law or any State law or Territory law, where a person has been granted a free and absolute pardon for a Commonwealth offence or a Territory offence because the person was wrongly convicted of the offence:</p> <p>(a) the person shall be taken, in any State or Territory, for all purposes, never to have been convicted of the offence; and</p> <p>(b) the person shall be taken, in a foreign country, by any Commonwealth authority or State authority in that country, for all purposes, never to have been convicted of the offence.</p> <p>(2) Despite any other Commonwealth law or any Territory law, where, under a State law or a foreign law a person is, in particular circumstances or for a particular purpose, to be taken never to have been convicted of an offence under a law of that State or foreign country:</p> <p>(a) the person shall be taken, in any Territory, in corresponding circumstances or for a corresponding purpose, never to have been convicted of that offence; and</p> <p>(b) the person shall be taken, in any State or foreign country, in corresponding circumstances or for a corresponding purpose, by any Commonwealth authority in that State or country, never to have been convicted of that offence.</p>
<p>If not</p> <p>Was the person either not sentenced to a term of imprisonment or to a term of imprisonment of less than 30 months?</p>	
<p>If so, has the waiting period passed?</p> <p>Has the period of 5 years passed beginning on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence, if the person was dealt with as a minor ; or has a court order in terms of s 85ZL extended the waiting period; or has the person been convicted (whether summarily or on indictment) by a court of a State (not being a court exercising</p>	<p>S 85ZL: waiting <i>period</i>, in relation to an offence, means:</p> <p>(a) if the person convicted of the offence was dealt with as a minor in relation to the conviction—the period of 5 years beginning on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence; or</p> <p>(b) in any other case—the period of 10 years beginning on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence.</p> <p>BUT, a court may lengthen that period if a further offence was committed:</p> <p>85ZX Convictions of further Commonwealth or Territory offences</p> <p>(1) Where:</p> <p>(a) Division 3 applies to a person in relation to an offence of which the person was convicted, or would (unless an order is made</p>

<p>federal jurisdiction) or a court of a foreign country, of another offence, being an offence committed during that waiting period?</p> <p>Or,</p> <p>In all other cases, has 10 years beginning on the day on which the person was convicted of the offence person is convicted (whether summarily or on indictment) by a court of a State (not being a court exercising federal jurisdiction) or a court of a foreign country, of another offence, being an offence committed during that waiting period?</p>	<p>under this section) so apply to the person if the waiting period for the offence had ended; and</p> <p>(b) before or after the end of the waiting period for the offence, the person is convicted summarily, by a court exercising federal jurisdiction or a court of a Territory, of another offence, being an offence committed during that waiting period;</p> <p>the court may order that Division 3 ceases to apply or does not apply to the person, as the case requires, in relation to the earlier offence until the waiting period for the later offence has ended.</p> <p>(2) Where:</p> <p>(a) Division 3 applies to a person in relation to an offence of which the person was convicted, or would (but for this subsection) so apply to the person if the waiting period for the offence had ended; and</p> <p>(b) before or after the end of the waiting period for the offence, the person is convicted on indictment, by a court exercising federal jurisdiction or a court of a Territory, of another offence, being an offence committed during that waiting period;</p> <p>Division 3 ceases to apply or does not apply to the person, as the case requires, in relation to the earlier offence until the waiting period for the later offence has ended.</p> <p>85ZY Convictions of further State or foreign offences</p> <p>Subject to subsection 85ZV(3), where:</p> <p>(a) Division 3 applies to a person in relation to an offence of which the person was convicted, or would so apply to the person if the waiting period for the offence had ended; and</p> <p>(b) before or after the end of the waiting period for the offence, the person is convicted (whether summarily or on indictment) by a court of a State (not being a court exercising federal jurisdiction) or a court of a foreign country, of another offence, being an offence committed during that waiting period;</p> <p>Division 3 ceases to apply or does not apply to the person, as the case requires, in relation to the earlier offence until the waiting period for the later offence has ended.</p>
--	--

If it is spent (and does not need to be disclosed by an agency) does it fall within one of the exceptions, allowing disclosure?

Working with children

<p>Is it disclosure to a prescribed person or body?</p> <p>If so, is that disclosure required or permitted by or under a prescribed Commonwealth law, a prescribed State law or a prescribed Territory law, to obtain and deal with information about persons who work, or seek to work, with children?</p> <p>If so, is the disclosure for the purpose of the person or body obtaining and dealing with such information in accordance with the prescribed law?</p> <p>OR</p> <p>If the disclosure is made by a prescribed person or body required or permitted by or under a prescribed Commonwealth law, a prescribed State law or a prescribed Territory law, to deal with information about persons who work, or seek to work, with children; AND</p> <p>the disclosure is required by or under a Commonwealth law, a State law or a Territory law.</p>	<p>85ZZGB Exclusion: disclosing information to a person or body</p> <p>Divisions 2 and 3 do not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to a prescribed person or body if:</p> <p>(a) the person or body is required or permitted by or under a prescribed Commonwealth law, a prescribed State law or a prescribed Territory law, to obtain and deal with information about persons who work, or seek to work, with children; and</p> <p>(b) the disclosure is for the purpose of the person or body obtaining and dealing with such information in accordance with the prescribed law.</p> <p>Prescribed: Under s 85ZZGE (Prescribed persons and bodies) by the Governor-General.</p> <p>Note: Find the instrument!</p> <p>85ZZGF Definitions</p> <p>In this Subdivision:</p> <p>child means a person who is under 18.</p> <p>work includes the following:</p> <p>(a) work:</p> <p>(i) under a contract of employment, contract of apprenticeship or contract for services; or</p> <p>(ii) in a leadership role in a religious institution, as part of the duties of a religious vocation or in any other capacity for the purposes of a religious institution; or</p> <p>(iii) as an officer of a body corporate, member of the committee of management of an unincorporated body or association or member of a partnership; or</p> <p>(iv) as a volunteer, other than unpaid work engaged in for a private or domestic purpose; or</p> <p>(v) as a self-employed person;</p> <p>(b) practical training as part of a course of education or vocational training;</p> <p>(c) acting in a prescribed capacity or engaging in a prescribed activity.</p>
--	---

	<p>Note: S 85ZZGC (Exclusion: person or body taking information into account) does not seem relevant to the use case</p> <p>85ZZGD Exclusion: person or body disclosing information</p> <p>Divisions 2 and 3 do not apply in relation to the disclosure of information by a prescribed person or body if:</p> <p>(a) the person or body is required or permitted by or under a prescribed Commonwealth law, a prescribed State law or a prescribed Territory law, to deal with information about persons who work, or seek to work, with children; and</p> <p>(b) the disclosure is required by or under a Commonwealth law, a State law or a Territory law.</p> <p>Note: The scheme was reviewed by the AGD in this report in 2013.</p>
<p>Law enforcement agency exceptions</p>	
<p>Is the request for information lodged by a law enforcement agency for the purpose of making decisions in relation to prosecution or sentencing?</p> <p>Is the request for information lodged by a law enforcement agency for the purpose of assessing prospective employees or prospective members of the agency?</p> <p>Is the request for information lodged by a law enforcement agency for the purpose of assessing persons proposed to be engaged as consultants to, or to perform services for, the agency or a member of the agency?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>(a) a law enforcement agency, for the purpose of making decisions in relation to prosecution or sentencing or of assessing:</p> <p>(i) prospective employees or prospective members of the agency; or</p> <p>(ii) persons proposed to be engaged as consultants to, or to perform services for, the agency or a member of the agency</p> <p>S 85ZL: law enforcement agency means:</p> <p>(a) the Australian Federal Police;</p> <p>(b) the police force of a State or Territory;</p> <p>ba) Customs;</p> <p>bb) the Australian Commission for Law Enforcement Integrity;</p> <p>(c) the ACC;</p> <p>(e) the CrimTrac Agency;</p> <p>(f) the Independent Commission Against Corruption established under the Independent Commission Against Corruption Act, 1988 of the State of New South Wales, or a similar body established under a law of another State;</p>

	<p>(g) the New South Wales Crime Commission established under the New South Wales Crime Commission Act 1985 of New South Wales, or a similar body established under a law of another State;</p> <p>(h) the Office of the Director of Public Prosecutions, or a similar body established under a State law;</p> <p>(j) a Director of Public Prosecutions, or a person performing a similar function, appointed under a law of a State;</p> <p>(k) staff appointed to assist a Director or person referred to in paragraph (j); or</p> <p>(m) officers or members of the Attorney-General’s Department of a State or a similar State Department, or of a body administered by such a Department, being officers or members whose primary function is the institution or conduct of proceedings for State offences.</p>
--	--

Intelligence or security agencies

<p>Is the request for information lodged by an intelligence or security agency for the purpose of assessing prospective employees or prospective members of the agency?</p> <p>Is the request for information lodged by an intelligence or security agency for the purpose of assessing persons proposed to be engaged as consultants to, or to perform services for, the agency or a member of the agency?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>(b) an intelligence or security agency, for the purpose of assessing:</p> <p>(i) prospective employees or prospective members of the agency; or</p> <p>(ii) persons proposed to be engaged as consultants to, or to perform services for, the agency or a member of the agency;</p> <p>S85ZL: intelligence or security agency means:</p> <p>(a) the Australian Security Intelligence Organisation; or</p> <p>(b) the Australian Secret Intelligence Service; or</p> <p>(c) the Office of National Assessments; or</p> <p>(d) that part of the Defence Department known as the Defence Signals Directorate; or</p> <p>(e) that part of the Defence Department known as the Defence Intelligence Organisation; or</p> <p>(f) that part of the Defence Department known as the Defence Imagery and Geospatial Organisation.</p>
---	--

A court or tribunal established under a Commonwealth law, a State law or a Territory Law

<p>Is the request for information lodged in relation to a court or tribunal established under a Commonwealth law, a State law or a Territory law, for the purpose of making a decision, including a decision in relation to sentencing?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>(c) a court or tribunal established under a Commonwealth law, a State law or a Territory law, for the purpose of making a decision, including a decision in relation to sentencing;</p>
<p>Immigration decisions</p>	
<p>Is the request for information lodged in relation to a person who makes a decision under the Migration Act 1958, the Australian Citizenship Act 2007, or the Immigration Act 1980 of the Territory of Norfolk Island, for the purpose of making that decision?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>(d) a person who makes a decision under the <i>Migration Act 1958</i>, the <i>Australian Citizenship Act 2007</i>, or the <i>Immigration Act 1980</i> of the Territory of Norfolk Island, for the purpose of making that decision;</p>
<p>Commonwealth authority appointments</p>	
<p>Is the request for information lodged in relation to a Commonwealth authority, for the purpose of assessing appointees or prospective appointees to a designated position?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>a Commonwealth authority, for the purpose of assessing appointees or prospective appointees to a designated position;</p> <p>S85ZL: Commonwealth authority means:</p> <p>(a) a Commonwealth Minister;</p> <p>(b) a Commonwealth Department;</p> <p>(ba) the Defence Force;</p> <p>(c) a body (whether incorporated or not), or a tribunal, established or appointed for a public purpose by or under a Commonwealth law, not being:</p> <p>(i) an incorporated company, society or association; or</p> <p>(ii) an organisation registered, or an association recognised, under the <i>Fair Work (Registered Organisations) Act 2009</i>, or a branch of such an organisation or association;</p>

	<p>(d) a body established or appointed by the Governor-General, or by a Commonwealth Minister, otherwise than by or under a Commonwealth law;</p> <p>(e) a person holding or performing the duties of an office established by or under, or an appointment made under, a Commonwealth law other than the office of Secretary of a Commonwealth Department;</p> <p>(f) a person holding or performing the duties of an appointment made by the Governor-General, or by a Commonwealth Minister, otherwise than under a Commonwealth law;</p> <p>(g) a federal court;</p> <p>(h) the Supreme Court of the Australian Capital Territory; or</p> <p>(j) the Australian Federal Police.</p> <p>designated position means a position in a Commonwealth authority which the head of the authority has determined to be a designated security assessment position whose duties are likely to involve access to national security information classified as secret or top secret.</p>
AUSTRAC	
<p>Is the request for information lodged in relation AUSTRAC, for the purpose of assessing prospective members of the staff of AUSTRAC?</p> <p>Is the request for information lodged in relation AUSTRAC for the purpose of assessing persons proposed to be engaged as consultants under subsection 225(1) of the <i>Anti-Money Laundering and Counter-Terrorism Financing Act 2006</i>?</p> <p>Is the request for information lodged in relation AUSTRAC for the purpose of assessing persons whose services are proposed to be made available to AUSTRAC under subsection 225(3) of the <i>Anti-Money Laundering and Counter-Terrorism Financing Act 2006</i>?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>AUSTRAC, for the purpose of assessing:</p> <p>(i) prospective members of the staff of AUSTRAC; or</p> <p>(ii) persons proposed to be engaged as consultants under subsection 225(1) of the <i>Anti-Money Laundering and Counter-Terrorism Financing Act 2006</i>; or</p> <p>(iii) persons whose services are proposed to be made available to AUSTRAC under subsection 225(3) of that Act;</p>

Solicitor-General	
<p>Is the request for information lodged in relation the Australian Government Solicitor, for the purpose of instituting or conducting proceedings for Commonwealth offences?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>the Australian Government Solicitor, for the purpose of instituting or conducting proceedings for Commonwealth offences;</p>
<p>Is the request for information lodged in relation to a prescribed person or body, for a prescribed purpose, in relation to a conviction for a prescribed offence?</p>	<p>85ZZH Exclusions</p> <p>Division 3 does not apply in relation to the disclosure of information to or by, or the taking into account of information by a person or body referred to in one of the following paragraphs for the purpose specified in relation to the person or body:</p> <p>a prescribed person or body, for a prescribed purpose, in relation to a conviction for a prescribed offence.</p> <p>Note: Check Crimes Regulations 1990 for prescriptions (https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/F2016C00955):</p> <p>Reg 8 Exclusions from Division 3 of Part VIIC of Act (Act s 85ZZH)</p> <p>(1) For the purposes of paragraph 85ZZH(k) of the Act, the persons and bodies specified in column 2 of Schedule 4 are prescribed for the purposes, and in relation to convictions for the offences, respectively specified in columns 3 and 4 of that Schedule in relation to those persons and bodies.</p> <p>(2) In Schedule 4, drug offence means an offence constituted by the production, possession, supply, importation or export of a substance that is:</p> <p>(a) a narcotic substance within the meaning of the <i>Customs Act 1901</i>; or</p> <p>(b) a drug within the meaning given by:</p> <p>(i) subregulation 9A(1) of the <i>Customs (Prohibited Exports) Regulations 1958</i>; or</p> <p>(ii) subregulation 5(20) of the <i>Customs (Prohibited Imports) Regulations 1956</i>.</p> <p>(3) In Schedule 4, designated offence has the meaning given by section 85ZL of the Act.</p> <p>And Schedule 4 has a hefty list of bodies, persons, purposes and offences: https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/F2016C00955</p>
Further exclusions	

Law enforcement agencies	
<p>Is the request for information lodged by a law enforcement agency, or an employee or member of a law enforcement agency, at another law enforcement agency, or an employee or member of another law enforcement agency, where the disclosure is made in the discharge of the duties of the first-mentioned agency, employee or member?</p> <p>Note: The other subsections are relevant to the request use case.</p>	<p>85ZZJ Further exclusions—law enforcement agencies</p> <p>(1) Division 3 does not apply in relation to:</p> <p>(a) the disclosure of information by a law enforcement agency, or an employee or member of a law enforcement agency, to another law enforcement agency, or an employee or member of another law enforcement agency, where the disclosure is made in the discharge of the duties of the first-mentioned agency, employee or member;</p> <p>(2) In this section:</p> <p>employee, in relation to a law enforcement agency, includes a person engaged as a consultant to, or to perform services for, the agency or a member of the agency.</p>
	<p>85ZZL Criminal proceedings before the Federal Court of Australia</p> <p>(1) The Federal Court of Australia (and an officer of that court) may</p> <p>(a) require a person to disclose information to the court, or an officer of the court, about any Commonwealth offence, State offence, Territory offence or foreign offence in relation to which the person has been charged or convicted; ...</p> <p>(2) Division 3 does not apply in relation to a disclosure of information, or a taking into account of information, under subsection (1).</p> <p>(4) For the purposes of references in this section to foreign law or foreign offence, a foreign country is taken to include a region where:</p> <p>(a) the region is a colony, territory or protectorate of a foreign country; or</p> <p>(b) the region is part of a foreign country; or</p> <p>(c) the region is under the protection of a foreign country; or</p> <p>(d) a foreign country exercises jurisdiction or control over the region; or</p> <p>(e) a foreign country is responsible for the region’s international relations.</p> <p>(5) In this section:</p>

	<p><i>criminal appeal proceedings</i> has the same meaning as in the <i>Federal Court of Australia Act 1976</i>.</p> <p><i>indictable primary proceedings</i> has the same meaning as in the <i>Federal Court of Australia Act 1976</i>.</p>
--	--

3 Elaborating on the analysis

3.1 Who, what, when, where, why, in what way, by what means?

We can start with the 5-6-7 basic questions in problem solving. Questions as put by classic Rhetoric: *Quis, quid, cur, quomodo, ubi, quando, quibus auxiliis*. (Aristotle, Quintilian, Boetius, Lullius, Agricola, Ramus etc. ...), or *Quis, quid, quando, ubi, cur, quem ad modum, quibus adminiculis*. Who, what, when, where, why, in what way, by what means, "[the seven circumstances fundamental to the arts of prosecution and defense](#)".

Dialectics, from the 16 c., was also understood as *locis communis* (common places) to construct ethical and legal cases. This is known as "problem solving" in the common law tradition, as Ramus' *Dialectics* (1555) served to set up the structure of the adversarial structure of the case law in 16 c. England.

This questioning is loosely followed by the so-called [Privacy fact sheet 41: Commonwealth spent convictions scheme](#), focusing on selected important issues (when, what, in what way, by what means) but skipping the subjects (who) and the reasons (why). This scheme is built to facilitate the comprehension of a quite complex legislation, covering many exceptions and targeting different scenarios and situations.

When is a conviction covered by the Scheme?

When is a conviction spent?

When does an individual have a right not to disclose their conviction?

What obligations apply to persons and authorities that handle information about convictions?

When must a spent conviction not be taken into account?

Obligations related to quashed convictions and pardons

What if the individual consents to the disclosure?

Exclusions

Interaction with the Privacy Act

What happens if someone has not complied with the Scheme?

Commonwealth spent convictions scheme: A step-by-step guide

For further information

Long text description

3.2 Definition

In UK 'spent convictions' are those convictions that have reached a set period and are removed from an individual's criminal record. Unspent convictions are those records that have not yet reached this defined time and will appear on a Basic Criminal Record Check.

In Australia it applies as well not to discriminate individuals in everyday life scenarios. "The aim of spent convictions legislation is to prevent discrimination on the basis of certain previous convictions. Spent convictions legislation limits the use and disclosure of older, less serious convictions and findings of guilt. Spent convictions of specific offences will be released where the check is required for certain purposes regardless of how old they are. Each Australian police agency will apply the relevant Spent Convictions legislation/information release policy prior to disclosure."

(https://www.nationalcrimecheck.com.au/resources/spent_convictions_information)

The National Crime Check provides the following definition:

"A "spent conviction" is a conviction of a Commonwealth, Territory, State or foreign offence that satisfies all of the following conditions: (i) it is 10 years since the date of the conviction (or 5 years for juvenile offenders); AND (ii) the individual was not sentenced to imprisonment or was not sentenced to imprisonment for more than 30 months; (iii) AND the individual has not re-offended during the 10 years (5 years for juvenile offenders) waiting period; (iv) AND a statutory or prescribed exclusion does not apply. (A full list of exclusions is available from the Office of the Australian Information Commissioner)."

The law affects Commonwealth authorities in the following ways: (i) a person with a conviction protected by Part VIIC *does not have* to disclose that conviction to any person, including a Commonwealth authority, unless an exclusion applies; (ii) Commonwealth authorities *are prohibited from* accessing, disclosing or taking into account spent convictions of Commonwealth offences.

4 Crimes Act 1914 (Part VIIC)

4.1. The scheme "allows an individual not to disclose certain criminal convictions in particular circumstances, and prohibits unauthorised use or disclosure of information about the conviction". I.e. individual right not to disclose + general prohibition of unauthorised disclosure of information.

Where (scope): "Scheme applies to convictions for less serious Commonwealth, state (including the Northern Territory and ACT) and foreign offences".

4.2. "Rights and obligations under the Scheme arise where an individual is convicted of a *less serious Commonwealth, state or foreign offence* and (i) it is a 'spent conviction', (ii) or the individual has been granted a 'pardon' in relation to

that conviction, (iii) or the conviction has been ‘quashed’” (a conviction that a court has set aside).

The Scheme does not apply to more serious convictions, where the individual has been sentenced to *imprisonment for more than 30 months*. (The individual has no right to object to the disclosure, i.e. he has to declare it when necessary).

4.3. Individuals are taken to have been convicted of an offence if: “(i) they have been convicted of the offence, (ii) or they have been found guilty of the offence but discharged without conviction, (iii) or they have not been found guilty of the offence but a court has taken it into account in sentencing them for another offence”.

4.4. The scope of rights and obligations under the Scheme will vary depending on: (i) whether the conviction is for a Commonwealth, state or foreign offence, (ii) who knows or is being told about a spent conviction, (iii) and where the person being told is located.

The waiting period is intended to demonstrate that an individual has been of ‘good behaviour’ since being convicted. (An individual who is convicted of a further offence committed during the waiting period will generally lose the right to have the earlier conviction treated as spent until the waiting period for the later conviction is ended).

5 When is a conviction spent?

5.1. “(i) the individual has been granted a pardon for a reason other than that the individual was wrongly convicted of the offence, (ii) or the individual was not sentenced to imprisonment for the offence (or not imprisoned for more than 30 months) and the waiting period for the offence has ended.”

5.2. “The waiting period is *ten years* beginning on the day on which the individual was convicted of the offence, or *five years* in the case of a juvenile offender (generally being a person under the age of 18 except in Queensland where it is under the age of 17).”

6 Limited right of non-disclosure: when does an individual have a right not to disclose their conviction?

Whether an individual has the right to not disclose their conviction will vary according to whether the conviction was for a Commonwealth, state or foreign offence, and the location and nature of the person or authority that is receiving information about the individual’s conviction history.

Table 1: Who can an individual not tell about their spent conviction?

Type of conviction	Recipient located in Australian external territory or Jervis Bay Territory	Recipient located in State (including the ACT and Northern Territory)	Recipient located in Foreign country
Conviction for a Commonwealth offence or an offence of an Australian external territory or Jervis Bay Territory	Any person	Any person	Commonwealth or state authority ^[3]
Conviction for a state offence (including ACT and Northern Territory offences)	Any person	Commonwealth authority	Commonwealth authority
Conviction for a foreign offence	Any person	Commonwealth authority	Commonwealth authority

7 Exclusions (Exception to the right)¹

It is unlawful for a person or authority to disclose an individual’s spent conviction or take it into account where the individual has a right of non-disclosure. Exceptions: in some circumstances the prohibitions on use and disclosure do not apply, for example those involving people who work with children. Exclusions (actually they might be represented as exceptions to the general right of non-disclosure).

(i) people working with children; (ii) law enforcement agencies for the purpose of: (a) making decisions in relation to prosecution or sentencing matters, (b) assessing prospective employees and consultants, (c) making certain disclosures to another law enforcement agency, (iii) AUSTRAC and intelligence or security agencies, for the purpose of assessing prospective employees and consultants, (iv) courts or tribunals making decisions, including sentencing decisions, (v) a person who makes a decision under *the Australian Citizenship Act 2007* or the *Migration Act 1958*.

8 Breaches (lodging a complaint)

An individual who believes that a **person** or a **Commonwealth or state authority** has breached the provisions of Part VIIC can [complain to the Office of the Australian Information Commissioner](#). In addition the [Australian Human Rights Commission can investigate a complaint](#) about [discrimination in employment based on a criminal record](#).

¹ See [Part VIIC, Division 6 of the Crimes Act 1914](#) and Regulations 7A and 8 and Schedule 3 of the [Crimes Regulations 1990](#).

9 Privacy Act 1988

Entities that are subject to the *Privacy Act 1988* must also ensure that they comply with their obligations under the Privacy Act when handling information about individuals' criminal convictions, for example, in relation to keeping the information secure and up to date. Authorities and persons who are not covered by the Privacy Act will still be subject to the provisions of Part VIIC; for example, small business operators.

10 Commonwealth Spent Convictions Scheme Guide²

Commonwealth spent convictions scheme: A step-by-step guide

*Note: a reference to a state includes a reference to the ACT and the Northern Territory.

** For the purposes of the Scheme, 'territory' means an Australian external territory or the Jervis Bay Territory.

² Source: Australian Government. <https://www.oaic.gov.au/individuals/privacy-fact-sheets/general/privacy-fact-sheet-41-commonwealth-spent-convictions-scheme>

11 Criticisms

11.1 What is the legal value of a 'scheme'

"Scheme" is a common word in legal drafting. The Black Law Dictionary defines "scheme" as "A broad outline of how an objective can be achieved. It is not a formal plan and will not show every detail."³ It is a descriptive but ambiguous concept that may refer to the outline, intention, backbone, content, effects, rationale, procedures or implementation of a legal doctrine, legal instrument, or policy. It is employed practically in all legal domains of the common law culture, either in USA, UK, Canada, NZ, or Australia.

"Scheme" has also been used according to several approaches, fields and topics. It has been typically objectivised as *argumentation schemes* (Gordon, 2007; Walton, Reed and Macagno, 2008)⁴, *regulatory* (Behm, 1999; Yanli, 2015), *practical* (Jacover, 2002), *statutory* (Inker and Clower, 1982; Kuehnle, 1988) or *hybrid* - combining private and public law- (Jung, 2012). In computation and IT legal studies, e.g., referring to *authentication schemes* is a common practice (Xiang, 2008).

We can approach the Spent Conviction Scheme (SCS) as primarily statutory. "A Statutory Scheme means an elaborate and systematic plan of action on a particular topic provided in the statute itself. It can be a specific Act or legislation dealing with a particular subject."⁵

Thus, it can be also described as a conceptual kernel apt to be deployed and eventually explained and justified to be implemented.

The first thing that should be noticed is that a 'scheme' belongs to the state, government or authorities implementation policy; it is not *per se* a law, or an act. Hence, it can shape and nuance the law implementation process, or even facilitate the legislative process.

Particularly in controversial matters, such as the implementation of drug legislation, legal scholars have noticed the many ways in which administrative or government schemes can become law and be applied. E.g. Lenton (2004) describes how evidence-based recommendations to decriminalize cannabis have become law in Western Australia (WA).⁶

³ <https://thelawdictionary.org/scheme/>

⁴ Argumentation schemes have a precise meaning in argumentation theory. They consist of argument (linguistic) forms that represent inferential structures of arguments used in political, legal, scientific or everyday discourses.

⁵ <https://definitions.uslegal.com/s/statutory-scheme/>

⁶ The Cannabis Control Bill 2003 passed the WA Parliament on 23 September. The Bill, the legislative backing behind the Cannabis Infringement Notice (CIN) Scheme, came into effect on 22 March 2004.

“Drug law reforms can be *de jure*, involving changes to the legal statutes themselves, or *de facto*, where the laws remain unchanged but the way the law is enforced by police is altered by administrative instructions. Prohibition with civil penalties schemes are examples of *de jure* reforms, while prohibition with cautioning and/or diversion schemes are examples of *de facto* reforms.”

Schemes are used to simplify, convey, discuss, interpret, and eventually draft legal content.

11.2 Spent Convictions

Royal Commission Report designed the spent convictions scheme in a Report released in 1987. It acknowledged the difficulties, and applied a proportionality principle to handle this issue:

“This report is concerned with the difficulties faced by former offenders arising out of their criminal records. An appropriate response must balance the offender's need to return to full citizenship against the public interest in the prevention and detection of crime, and in appropriate decision making in judicial and other contexts. The Commission's general conclusion is that these difficulties may be appropriately reduced, if not avoided, by: (i) minimising the negative consequences that attach to old (spent) convictions, (ii) making it unlawful to discriminate unreasonably against a person on the basis of his or her criminal record, (iii) and establishing controls on the collection, storage and dissemination of criminal record information by the police and by other record keepers”.

Hence, “The Commission re-iterates its recommendation in the Criminal Investigation report that there be a specialist, multi-disciplinary task force to develop rules controlling criminal record keeping and checking on a national basis.”

Several recommendations followed to balance protections and official powers:

Recommendation 4: “References in Commonwealth laws and the laws of the Territories (other than the Northern Territory and Norfolk Island) to convictions *should be interpreted as not including reference to spent convictions unless there is express legislative provision to the contrary.*”

Recommendation 5: “Spent convictions should generally not be able to be taken into account in making decisions about the offender, **whether in a legal context or not**. This rule should also apply to facts about spent convictions, including the fact that the person committed an offence, or was arrested or charged with an offence which is the subject of a spent conviction.”

Several remedies and exceptions were envisaged in successive recommendations. General remedies already in place were deemed to be sufficient, as “it is not appropriate that failure to comply with the obligation should attract a criminal penalty. Other remedies available, including injunctions, declarations, and judicial

and administrative review of decisions, offer more appropriate relief. (Recommendation 6). Exceptions were wider:

Recommendation 7: “There should be specific exemptions for the Australian Federal Police and Commonwealth agencies when exercising powers in relation to national security and criminal intelligence. The courts should be authorised expressly to continue to use spent convictions in sentencing. Obligations to have regard to spent convictions that are expressly imposed **by** statute should continue to have effect.”

Recommendation 12: “Where the relevance of a particular spent conviction to decision making, and the public interest in having it available to be used, is clearly demonstrated, it should be possible for the decision maker to be exempted from aspects of the scheme.”

11.3 Critical scholarship

The doctrine has been quite critical with the SCE, which has been considered insufficient to reach the objectives of protecting offenders’ rights and facilitating their rehabilitation and reintegration in society. Wrong convictions and spent convictions are a sensitive issue and have drawn the attention of criminologists. Weathered (2005, p. 203, see also 2007) stressed the “length of time and difficulties that can be experienced in achieving an exoneration”.⁷ Hammer (2014, p. 311) observes that “analyses of DNA exonerations in the US suggest that the wrongful conviction rate is three per cent or higher [...], there is no reason to believe the error rate in Australia would be radically lower.” Dioso-Villa (2015) recently collected a complete listing of 71 identified and known wrongful convictions in Australia from 1922 to 2015. She concludes that “all jurisdictions lack any systematic recording and collection of data on successful appeals that can identify potential wrongful conviction in need of further investigation” (ibid. 2015, p. 194).

Scholarship on spent convictions follows the same critical path, linking the scheme to resocialization and integration purposes.

“Australia’s historical and legal origins offer no generous philosophy of resocialization, by contrast with for example France, Germany, Spain and the Netherlands, and can provide only indirect mechanisms for rewarding desistance. Especially in the absence of human rights courts. [...] For a country settled by

⁷ “John Button in Western Australia, was convicted of the manslaughter of his girlfriend Rosemary Anderson. While he spent approximately five years incarcerated for this crime, he spent almost four decades fighting to prove his innocence. Button discovered Anderson lying wounded on the side of the road. After racing her to a doctor he was subjected to an intense police interrogation. During this interrogation a false confession was made, but was retracted shortly afterwards. Subsequently, a known and convicted serial killer, Eric Edgar Cooke, later on several occasions confessed to the murder of Anderson providing full details of the incident.” (Weathered, 2005, p. 203).

white colonisers for the warehousing of convicts, Australia is remarkably reluctant to forgive. [...] (Naylor, 2011, p. 80)

Naylor raise the problems of the Internet records and usage, which cannot be ignored and is related to privacy issues as well. "Anyone can collect, store and make available criminal history information gleaned from the media, published judgments, and any other public information". (ibid. 83). Restrictions apply, but there are a number of private providers serving this kind of information.⁸

Employment and labour opportunities are affected. "Offenders who are employed in certain industries, especially the professions, often suffer a far greater net punishment upon being found guilty of a criminal offence than other offenders, thereby violating the principle of proportionality and the (related) principle of equality in the impact of sanctions." (Bagaric, 2004, p. 329)

But Australian privacy laws protect personal information (such as a criminal history) from release to third parties without the owner's consent. Any employer request for criminal history information therefore requires the applicant to obtain their criminal history information themselves and provide this to the employer (Naylor, 2011). Privacy, anti-discrimination laws and spent convictions are in fact the chain of custody for individuals' rights, but with a limited effectivity according to the doctrine.

Kilcommins and O'Donnell (2003) identified three models: (i) *Discriminatory model*: prohibits discrimination on the grounds of a criminal record in relation to a variety of activities including employment; (ii) *Spent convictions model*: offences are expunged after prescribed qualifying periods; (iii) *Hybrid model*: provision is made for the elimination of discrimination on the grounds of an irrelevant criminal record (as provided under spent convictions legislation).

Scholars have also highlighted the problems of organisation and lack of cooperation of police bodies (Legal Enforcement Agencies, LEA). According to Hufnagel (2012), practitioners may overcome the negative attitude of their organisations and develop personal networks which transcend borders. However, on the other hand, they can embody the obstructive attitude of the organisation he/she represents.

12 Australia Human Rights Commission on Spent Convictions (2008)

The Model Spent Convictions Bill ('Model Bill') was developed by the Standing Committee of Attorneys-General ('SCAG') to provide for a uniform national spent convictions regime. The Australian Human Rights Commission (2009)

⁸ "CrimeNet claims that „We work within the law" and that it has systems in place to ensure compliance with „spent convictions" schemes, but asserts on its webpage: „Details of criminal convictions are public records in most Western democracies and it is a generally accepted principle of privacy rights that this information should always be accessible." Ibid.

pronounced four clear statements about it, commenting on the draft of the 2009 Bill: (i) “The model Spent Convictions Bill should apply to all convictions. The Commission considers the eligibility requirements for the scheme to be unduly restrictive.” (ii) “The exemptions to the scheme are too widely cast. If these exemptions are retained in the Bill they should be balanced by the introduction of protections at a federal level from unlawful criminal record discrimination.” (iii) “Clause 11(4)(d) contains no enforcement mechanism or grievance procedure. A person who is refused employment because of a spent conviction in breach of clause 11(4)(d) has no remedy under the draft Bill. (iv) “The implementation of the model Spent Convictions Bill should be accompanied by a comprehensive community education strategy”.

13 Wales and England (Rehabilitation of Offenders Act 1974)

<http://hub.unlock.org.uk/knowledgebase/spent-and-unspent-convictions-when-you-might-have-to-disclose-them/>

“Spent convictions are those convictions that have reached a set period as defined by the Rehabilitation of Offenders Act 1974, and are removed from an individual's criminal record. Unspent convictions are those records that have not yet reached this defined time and will appear on a Basic Criminal Record Check”.

As stated by UK Government, convictions and criminal records can have an impact in a range of ways. Table 2 summarises the areas in which spent/or unspent convictions might have a greater impact.

Table 2: Areas of life, according to the interpretation of UK Rehabilitation Offenders Act (1974)

Area of life	Unspent	Spent
Employment (approaches of specific professions, regulators and membership bodies are available on our Hub)	If asked by an employer, you have to disclose	For most jobs/roles, you don't need to disclose, even if they ask about convictions – this is for roles covered by the ROA For some jobs/roles, you will normally need to disclose them (unless its filtered) – these will usually involve a standard or enhanced check
	Can be taken into account by an employer - it's up to them to decide how relevant it is	For most jobs/roles, they should not be taken into account (they shouldn't even know about them)
		For some jobs/roles, they can be taken into account by an employer (unless it's filtered) – it's up to them to decide how relevant it is
		For some jobs/roles (e.g. police) filtered cautions and convictions can also be taken into account
	Any employer can do a basic disclosure, which shows unspent convictions	Not disclosed on a basic disclosure
	Disclosed on standard and enhanced checks	Disclosed on standard and enhanced checks (unless filtered)
Volunteering	Similar to employment (above)	Similar to employment (above)
	Becoming a trustee of a charity (only dishonesty or deception offences)	You do not need to disclose spent convictions when looking to become a trustee of a charity
Education and training	If asked, you have to disclose when applying for College, University and other employment-related qualifications	You don't have to disclose (unless the course involves a placement that would be eligible for standard or enhanced checks, or completion of a course allows entry into an exempt profession)
Insurance	If asked, you have to disclose when buying personal insurance	You don't have to disclose when applying for any type of insurance
	You need to provide unspent convictions as a 'material fact' for commercial insurance (even if not asked)	
Housing	If asked, you have to disclose when applying to rent a house (e.g. council house, housing association or private rented) or looking at getting a mortgage	You don't have to disclose when applying for any type of housing
Travel abroad	Whether a conviction is spent or not is irrelevant. Your conviction will be treated in line with the guidelines that the country you're travelling to has in place	
Travel to the UK and applying for citizenship	Whether a conviction is spent or not is irrelevant. There are separate guidelines on how convictions will be treated for immigration and citizenship decisions	
Victim of a crime	If you're a victim of a crime and are looking to apply for compensation from the Criminal Injuries Compensation Authority, you will have your entitlement reduced	You don't have to disclose if you're a victim of a crime and are looking for compensation from the Criminal Injuries Compensation Authority
Police records	Whether a conviction is spent or not is irrelevant. The police hold details of all cautions and convictions on the Police National Computer until you reach 100 years old.	

14 References

- Australian Government (2014). *Privacy fact sheet 41. Commonwealth spent convictions scheme*. May.
- Bagaric, M., 2004. The disunity of employment law and sentencing. *The Journal of Criminal Law*, 68 (4), pp.329-355.
- Behm, L. L. (1997). Legal, Moral & International Perspectives on Surrogate Motherhood: The Call for a Uniform Regulatory Scheme in the United States." *DePaul J. Health Care L.* 2: 557-604.
- Dioso-Villa, R., 2015. A repository of wrongful convictions in Australia: first steps toward estimating prevalence and causal contributing factors. *Flinders LJ*, 17, p.163. Gerber, P., O'Byrne, K. (2013). Should Gay Men Still be Labelled Criminals? *Alternative Law Journal* 38(2) *Alternative Law Journal*, 38 (2), pp. 82-86.
- Gordon, T.F. Constructing arguments with a computational model of an argumentation scheme for legal rules: interpreting legal rules as reasoning policies. *Proceedings of the 11th international conference on Artificial intelligence and law*. ACM, 2007.
- Hamer, D., 2014. Wrongful convictions, appeals, and the finality principle: The need for a criminal cases review commission. *UNSWLJ*, 37, p.270-311.
- Hufnagel, S., 2012. Harmonising police cooperation laws in Australia and the European Union: the tension between local/national and national/supranational interests. *Australian Journal of Forensic Sciences*, 44(1), pp.45-62.
- Inker, M. L., Clower, M.A. (1982). Towards a New Justice in Martial Dissolution: The Massachusetts Statutory Scheme and Due Process Analysis. *Suffolk UL Rev.* 16: 907-936.
- Jung, J.W. (2012). Nudging Websites: A Proposal for a Hybrid Regulatory Scheme to Enforce Online Copyright. *ISJLP*, 8: 149-177.
- Kilcommins, S. and O'Donnell, I., 2003. Wiping the slate clean: Rehabilitating offenders and protecting the public. *Administration*, vol. 51, no. 3 (Autumn 2003), 73-89.
- Knowler, J. (1994). Living down the past – spent convictions schemes in Australia. *Privacy Law and Policy Reporter*.
- Kuehnle, W.H., (1988). Secondary Liability Under the Federal Securities Laws-Aiding and Abetting, Conspiracy, Controlling Person, and Agency: Common-Law Principles and the Statutory Scheme. *J. Corp. L.*, 14: 313-376.
- Lam, H. and Harcourt, M. (2003). The use of criminal record in employment decisions: The rights of ex-offenders, employers and the public. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 47(3), pp.237-252.
- Lenton, S. (2004). Pot, politics and the press—reflections on cannabis law reform in Western Australia. *Drug and alcohol review*, 23(2), pp.223-233.
- Naylor, B. (2005). Do Not Pass Go: The impact of criminal record checks on employment in Australia, *Alternative Law Journal* 30 (4), pp. 174-179.
- Naylor, B. (2011). Criminal records and rehabilitation in Australia. *European Journal of Probation*, 3 (1), pp.79-96.

- Naylor, B., Paterson, M., Pittard, M. (2008). 'In the shadow of a Criminal Record: Proposing a Just Model of Criminal Record Employment Checks' *Melbourne University Law Review* 32 (1): 171. Available at: <http://www5.austlii.edu.au/au/journals/MelbULawRw/2008/6.html>
- Paterson, M. and Naylor, B. (2011). Australian spent convictions reform: A contextual analysis. *UNSWLJ*, 34, pp. 938-963.
- Paterson, M., 'Criminal Records, Spent Convictions and Privacy: A Trans-Tasman Comparison' (2011) 69 *New Zealand Law Review*.
- South Australia. Spent Convictions Act 2009. Version: 30.4.2018.
- South Australia. Spent Convictions Regulations 2011. under the Spent Convictions Act 2009, Version: 23.8.2018.
- The Law Reform Commission (1987). *Spent Convictions*. Report n. 37. Australian Government Publishing Service, Canberra.
- Walton, D., Reed, C. and Macagno, F. (2008). *Argumentation schemes*. Cambridge University Press.
- Weathered, L., 2005. Pardon me: Current avenues for the correction of wrongful conviction in Australia. *Current Issues Crim. Just.*, 17, p.203-216.
- Xiang, T., Wong, K.W. and Liao, X. (2008). Cryptanalysis of a password authentication scheme over insecure networks. *Journal of Computer and system Sciences*, 74(5): 657-661.
- Yanli, W. (2015). P2P Development and Regulatory Scheme in China. *China Legal Sci.*, 3: 24-48.